

Azo Dyes from Cashewnut Shell Liquid Derivatives. Part II. Azo Dyes from 5-Pentadecylresorcinol

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5-Pentadecylresorcinol, a hydrogenated derivative of a component of cashewnut shell liquid, has been coupled with *p*-methoxybenzenediazonium chloride. Two monoazo and two disazo dyes have been obtained and their position isomerism has been thoroughly investigated. The structures of the monoazo and disazo dyes have been arrived at by comparing their absorption spectra and mode of formation of copper complexes with those of monoazo and disazo dyes of resorcinol.

Cardol, the vesicant component, is present to the extent of 10% in cashewnut shell liquid'. Backer and Haack² obtained tetrahydrocardol by hydrogenating cardol and assigned to it the following structure.

p-Anisidine was diazotised and coupled with 5-pentadecylresorcinol in presence of sodium hydroxide. A mixture of dyes was obtained on acidification. As isolation of the pure dyes was rather difficult by crystallisation, separation of the dyes was attempted by chromatography on a column of activated alumina. As many as 8 to 10 bands were observed. On elution, three monoazo dyes were isolated along with a number of other azo dyes, which could not be identified as monoazo or disazo due to their very low yields. *Cis-trans* isomerism of azo dyes may account for the large number of compounds indicated to be present. Since the yields of many of these possible *cis-trans* isomers were extremely low and the separation on chromatography column was rather erratic, investigations were confined only to the dyes which were obtained in major quantities by crystallisations.

The mixture of dyes obtained on repeating the experiment was therefore subjected to crystallisation, when chocolate-coloured needles of a disazo dye, m.p. 125-26°, and orange-red needles of a monoazo dye, m.p. 100-101°, were obtained.

The structure of the orange-red monoazo dye (m.p. 100-101°) could be either 4-(*p*-methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (I) or 2-(*p*-methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (II).

1. Städeler, *Annalen*, 1847, 63, 137.

2. *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1941, 60, 661.

The disazo dye could be either 2,4-bis-(III) or 4:6-bis-(*p*-methoxybenzene)-azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (IV).

When *p*-anisidine was diazotised and the diazonium chloride was coupled with 5-pentadecylresorcinol in presence of sodium acetate, two more isomers, viz., (i) a red-coloured disazo dye, m.p. 106-107° and (ii) a bright red-coloured monoazo dye, m.p. 108-108.5°, were obtained in addition to (iii), an orange-red monoazo dye, m.p. 100-101° (*vide supra*).

Structures of the Monoazo Dyes (I & II)

Theoretically monoazo dye from 5-pentadecylresorcinol would have one of the following structures: 4-*p*-methoxybenzeneazo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (I) or 2-*p*-methoxybenzeneazo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (II). The assignment of structures was made on the following observations.

(i). *Absorption Spectra of the Monoazo Dyes of 5-Pentadecylresorcinol*.—It is known that *para*-substitution in benzeneazophenol enhances the intensity of absorbance and the *ortho*-substituents reduce it due to steric hindrance³. It was therefore thought that the absorption curves of the monoazo dyes would help in deciding their position isomerism. Both of them, however, provided almost identical curves and hence these data were not useful in assigning the constitution. The absorption curve of

3. Symposium on "Recent Advances in the Chemistry of Colouring Matters", The Chemical Society, Special publication No. 4, 1956, p. 4.

monazo dye (m.p. 100-101°) has one maximum at 2570 Å (ϵ , 9486) and the other maximum at 4370 Å (ϵ , 23820). The other isomer (m.p. 108-108.5°) has one maximum in the UV region at 2570 Å (ϵ , 10220) and the other maximum in the visible region at 4370 Å (ϵ , 22730).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The absorption maxima of both these dyes are shifted towards the longer wave length as compared to the 2-azo and 4-azo isomers of the resorcinol dye. This shift may be due to the additional methoxyl substituent.

(ii). *Co-ordination Copper Complexes of the Monoazo Dyes of 5-Pentadecylresorcinol and Resorcinol.*—It is well known that the *ortho*-hydroxyazo compounds form co-ordination compounds by implicating a metal atom in either a six-membered or a five-

membered chelate ring. Generally only one nitrogen atom of the azo linkage enters into co-ordination to form a six-membered chelate ring, though in some cases both the nitrogen atoms of the azo linkage have been shown to co-ordinate with two metal atoms to form a 6-membered and a 5-membered chelate ring⁴.

It has been further shown that the copper complexes of the *oo'*-dihydroxyazobenzene are co-ordinatively unsaturated and form saturated addition compounds with one molecule of aniline or pyridine⁵.

As 4-azoresorcinol would have only one hydroxyl group for chelation with the azo linkage and 2-azoresorcinol would have two such groups for chelation, it was thought that the formation of copper complexes might help in deciding the position isomerism of the monoazo dyes (m.p. 100-101° and 108-108.5°). 4- & 2-Benzeneazoresorcinols⁶ were prepared and their mode of formation of copper complexes was studied.

In the case of 4-benzeneazoresorcinol, the analytical data show that the desired complex (V) is always associated with a small amount of impurity, which is probably complex (VI). Further experiments, using larger quantities of copper acetate, were not of much help in avoiding the formation of (VI).

When an ethanolic solution of 2-benzeneazoresorcinol was allowed to react with ethanolic copper acetate in the molar proportion of 1:2 in presence of ammonia, a dark brown copper complex was obtained, m.p. > 360°. The analytical data show that two atoms of copper take part in the formation of the chelate compound with one molecule of

4. Beech and Drew, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 608.

5. Drew and Landquist, *ibid.*, 1938, 292.

6. Gore and Venkataraman, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951 34A, 368.

the dye. Structure (VII) is therefore assigned to the dye. The quantity of the dye being too small, the addition compounds with aniline and pyridine could not be prepared.

Similar experiments were carried out with 4-azo- and 2-azo-5-pentadecylresorcinols and the mode of formation of their complexes was studied. The monoazo dye (m.p. 100-101°) yielded a copper complex (VIII), m.p. 295-97° (decomp.) when equimolar ethanolic solutions of the dye and copper acetate were allowed to react in presence of ammonia. Analytical data correspond to the molecular formula $C_{28}H_{40}O_3N_2Cu(OH)_2$, showing that one atom of Cu chelates with one molecule of the azo dye. The presence of the unsaturated co-ordinate valency has been shown by preparing the addition compounds (IX), m.p. 252-54° (decomp.), and (X), m.p. 194° (decomp.), containing one molecule of aniline and one molecule of pyridine respectively.

An attempt was made to obtain a copper complex containing two atoms of copper by using double the quantity of copper acetate. Analytical data show that the material obtained is not a single entity. It was observed that the pyridine-addition compound (VII) had a tendency to lose the pyridine molecule when dried in vacuum at higher than room temperature. The material was therefore dissolved in pyridine, the filtered solution evaporated to dryness, and dried in vacuum at 100° when a copper complex, m.p. 294-97° (decomp.), was obtained. The analytical data correspond to the molecular formula of (VIII). This monoazo dye is thus incapable of yielding a copper complex containing two atoms of copper and has been assigned structure (I).

The monoazo dye (m.p. 108-108.5°) yielded copper complex (XI), m.p. >360°, when equimolar solutions of the dye and copper acetate in dioxane were allowed to react. It has been assigned structure (XI) on the basis of analytical data corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{28}H_{40}O_3N_2Cu_2(OH)_2$. Thus two atoms of copper enter into the formation of a chelate compound with one molecule of the azo dye. The quantity of the complex being too small, the addition compounds were not worked out. Incidentally, the yield of the monoazo dye (m.p. 108-108.5°) was extremely low

(dye m.p. 100-101°; 80% and 108-108.5°; 0.4%). Thus the monoazo dye (m.p. 108-108.5°) has been assigned structure (II).

Structures of the Disazo Dyes (III & IV)

A disazo dye from 5-pentadecylresorcinol would have one of the following two structures, 2,4-bis-(III) or 4,6-bis-*p*-methoxybenzeneazo-5-pentadecylresorcinol (V).

(i). *Mode of Formation of the Disazo Dyes of 5-Pentadecylresorcinol.*—It is known that when benzenediazonium chloride is coupled with resorcinol in presence of alkali, 4,6-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol is formed. When coupling is carried out in presence of sodium acetate, 2,4-bis-dye⁶ is obtained. In analogy with the above observations, the compound, m.p. 125-26°, obtained from 5-pentadecylresorcinol on coupling in presence of alkali, is assigned 4,6-disazo structure (IV). The other disazo dye, m.p. 106-107°, obtained when the coupling is carried out in presence of sodium acetate, is formulated as the 2,4-disazo isomer (III).

Although the colour of the dye may not be a definite criterion in deciding the position isomerism, it may be pointed out that the compound (II, m.p. 125-26°) has a chocolate colour like that of 4,6-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol and the compound (I, m.p. 106-107°) has a red colour like that of 2,4-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol. These observations also lead to the same conclusions regarding the structures of the disazo dyes.

(ii). *Absorption Spectra of the Disazo Dyes of 5-Pentadecylresorcinol.*—The absorption spectra of these dyes compare well with 2,4- and 4,6-disazo dyes of resorcinol.

The absorption curve of the dye (III, m.p. 106-107°) has one maximum at 4620 Å (ϵ , 46060) in the visible region, like 2,4-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol⁷ which also has one maximum at 4150 Å (ϵ , 60,000) in the visible region. The maximum of the dye of 5-pentadecylresorcinol is shifted to the longer wave length, compared to those of the dyes of resorcinol. Such a shift would be expected of a dye having a methoxyl group in *para* position. This confirms structure (III), i.e., 2,4-disazo structure for the dye, m.p. 106-107°.

The absorption curve of the dye (m.p. 125-26°) has two maxima, one at 3750 Å (ϵ , 40000) and the other at 4450 Å (ϵ , 33500)

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

disazo structure for the dye melting at 125-26°.

in the visible region, like 4,6-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol⁷, which also has two maxima, one at 3250 Å (ϵ , 30000) and the other at 4150 Å (ϵ , 20,000) in the visible region. The maxima of the dye of 5-pentadecylresorcinol are shifted to the longer wave length as in the case of its isomer, the reason for which is already explained above. This confirms structure (IV), i.e., 4,6-

Thus comparison of the absorption spectra, mode of formation, and shades of these two disazo dyes with the disazo dyes of rosorcinol suggest that the lower melting dye (m.p. 106-107°) is a 2,4-disazo isomer (III) and the higher melting dye (m.p. 125-126°) is a 4,6-disazo isomer (IV).

EXPERIMENTAL

4,6-Bis-(p-methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol—*p*-Anisidine (0.31 g.) was diazotised and the diazonium chloride solution (50 ml) was coupled with 5-pentadecylresorcinol (0.8 g.), dissolved in ethanol (75 ml) containing aqueous 10*N*-NaOH solution (1.5 ml). The dye (1.02 g.), precipitated on acidification with 10% HCl (dil.), was crystallised four times from ethanol as chocolate needles, m.p. 125-26°, yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 71.40; H, 8.01; N, 9.71. $C_{35}H_{48}O_4N_4$ requires C, 71.39; H, 8.22; N, 9.52%).

4-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—The solid, obtained on diluting the mother liquor of the above experiment, was crystallised thrice from dilute ethanol (80%), to provide orange needles of the monoazo dye, m.p. 100-101°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 74.40; H, 9.41; N, 6.17. $C_{28}H_{42}O_3N_2$ requires C, 73.97; H, 9.31; N, 6.16%).

2,4-Bis-(p-methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—*p*-Anisidine (12.3 g.) was diazotised and the diazonium chloride solution (90 ml) was coupled with an ethanolic solution (230 ml) of 5-pentadecylresorcinol (32.0 g.) containing aqueous sodium acetate (40 g. in 60 ml). The solid, precipitated on acidification with 10% HCl (dil., 42.49 g.), was washed well with water and crystallised from excess of ethanol (600 ml). The first crop was separated and crystallised twice from ethanol to furnish brick-red, microscopic needles of the disazo dye, m.p. 106-107°, yield 3.02 g. (Found: C, 71.15; H, 8.13; N, 9.62. $C_{35}H_{48}O_4N_4$ requires C, 71.39; H, 8.22; N, 9.52%).

2-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—The mother liquors of crystallisation from the above experiment were combined and concentrated to about one-third the volume and the second crop was collected. It was then suspended in ethanol (250 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for about 20 min. The solution was filtered hot and the undissolved dye was washed with ethanol (15 ml) and crystallised twice from dilute acetone in red needles of the monoazo dye, m.p. 108-108.5°, yield 0.08 g. Its mixed m.p. with the compound of m.p. 106-107° showed a depression. (Found: C, 74.4; H, 9.36; N, 6.42. $C_{28}H_{42}O_3N_2$ requires C, 73.97; H, 9.31; N, 6.16%).

4-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—The solid obtained on evaporating the mother liquors of the above experiment was fractionally crystallised from 80% EtOH as orange needles of the monoazo dye, m.p. 100-101°, yield 16.2 g. Its mixed m.p. with the compounds (m.p. 106-107° and 108-108.5°) showed depressions, but with the monoazo dye from the second experiment showed no depression. (Found: C, 74.40; H, 9.41; N, 6.17. $C_{28}H_{42}O_3N_2$ requires C, 73.97; H, 9.31; N, 6.16%).

Additional quantity of the disazo dye, m.p. 106-107°, was recovered during fractional crystallisation (yield 0.52 g.).

2 & 4-Benzeneazoresorcinols were prepared by the method of Gore and Venkataraman⁸ and 2,4-bis-benzeneazoresorcinol, according to Kostanecki⁹.

Co-ordinatively Unsaturated Copper Complex having one Copper Atom from 4-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—To a solution of the dye (2.61 g.) in ethanol (300 ml) containing liquor ammonia (5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring an ethanolic copper acetate solution (230 ml, 0.5%). The solution was filtered and cooled overnight. The dark brown powder of the complex was filtered and washed alternatively with water and ethanol. It could not be crystallised; m.p. 295-97° (decomp.), yield 1.7 g. (Found: C, 62.64; H, 7.30; N, 5.58; residue, 14.61. $C_{28}H_{42}O_4N_2Cu$ requires C, 63.04; H, 7.88; N, 5.25; residue, 14.82%).

Addition Compound with Aniline of the Copper Complex (m.p. 295-97°).—The above complex (10.87 g.) was dissolved in a little excess of boiling aniline and the solution was filtered hot through a sintered glass funnel. The addition compound separated on cooling the solution overnight at less than 5°. The addition compound was washed well with ethanol to remove the excess aniline. It could not be recrystallised; m.p. 252-54° (decomp.), yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 65.4; H, 7.32; N, 6.81; residue, 12.92. $C_{34}H_{49}O_4N_3Cu$ requires C, 65.18; H, 7.82; N, 6.71; residue, 12.62%).

Addition Compound with Pyridine of the Copper Complex (m.p. 295-97°).—The above complex (0.21 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml). The solution was filtered and evaporated at room temperature. The residue obtained was washed well with light petroleum (40-60°) to remove traces of pyridine. It could not be crystallised; m.p. 194° (decomp.), yield 0.16 g. It had a tendency to lose the pyridine molecule on heating and hence it was dried at room temperature in vacuum. (Found: C, 64.13; H, 7.14; N, 6.44; residue, 11.82. $C_{33}H_{47}O_4N_3Cu$ requires C, 64.7; H, 7.67; N, 6.86; residue, 12.9%).

Attempt to Prepare a Co-ordinatively Unsaturated Copper Complex having Two Copper Atoms from 4-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—To a solution of the dye (0.26 g.) in ethanol (30 ml) containing liquor ammonia (0.5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring an ethanolic copper acetate solution (23 ml, 1%). The solution was filtered and cooled overnight. The dark brown powder was filtered and washed alternatively with water and ethanol. It could not be crystallised; a part of the compound melted at 250-54°; yield 0.19 g. (Found: C, 50.73; H, 6.35; N, 4.21; residue, 28.32. $C_{28}H_{42}O_5N_4Cu_2$ requires C, 54.9; H, 6.86; N, 4.58; residue, 25.82%; $C_{28}H_{42}O_4N_2Cu$ requires C, 63.04; H, 7.88; N, 5.25; residue, 14.82%).

The solid was dissolved in pyridine and filtered. The residue was rejected. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The solid obtained was washed well with light petroleum and ethanol and dried in vacuum at 100°; m.p. 294-97° (decomp.), yield 0.09 g. (Found: C, 62.11; H, 7.23; N, 5.6; residue, 15.6. $C_{28}H_{42}O_4N_2Cu$ requires C, 63.04; H, 7.88; N, 5.25; residue, 14.82%).

Co-ordinatively Unsaturated Copper Complex having Two Atoms of Copper from 2-(p-Methoxybenzene)azo-5-pentadecylresorcinol.—To a solution of the dye (0.07 g.) in dilute acetone (20 ml, 80%) containing liquor ammonia (0.25 ml) was added dropwise with stirring an ethanolic copper acetate solution (18 ml, 0.5%). The solution was filtered and

8. Ber., 1887, 20, 3137; 1898, 21, 3118.

diluted with water (30ml) when the complex separated; it was filtered. It could not be crystallised. It was purified by alternate washings with water and dilute acetone; m.p. $> 360^\circ$, yield 0.06 g. (Found: C, 55.91; H, 7.22; N, 4.8; residue, 24.7. $C_{23}H_{42}O_5N_2Cu_2$ requires C, 54.9; H, 6.86; N, 4.58; residue, 25.82%).

Attempts to Prepare Co-ordinatively Unsaturated Copper Complex having One Copper Atom from 4-Benzeneazoresorcinol.—(a). To a solution of 4-benzeneazoresorcinol (1.07g.) in dioxane (40 ml) containing liquor ammonia (2.5ml) was added dropwise with stirring copper acetate solution in dilute dioxane (10 ml, 10%). The mixture was filtered and cooled overnight. Since the complex did not separate, the solution was evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The brown solid obtained (1.5g.) was washed well with chloroform and water. It could not be crystallised; m.p., $> 360^\circ$, yield 0.6g. (Found: C, 50.37; H, 4.0; N, 9.8; residue, 22.12. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3N_2Cu$ requires C, 49.14; H, 3.41; N, 9.55; residue, 26.96. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4N_4Cu$ requires C, 58.89; H, 3.68; N, 11.45; residue, 16.15%).

Analytical results showed that the complex was not pure. It could not be further purified even with several washings with chloroform and water.

(b). To a solution of 4-benzeneazoresorcinol (0.46 g.) in dioxane (30ml) containing liquor ammonia (1.5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring copper acetate (0.9 g.) solution in dilute dioxane (30 ml, 3%). The mixture was filtered and cooled overnight. Since the complex did not separate, the solution was evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The brown solid obtained was washed well with chloroform and water. It could not be crystallised; m.p. $> 360^\circ$, yield 0.7g. (Found: C, 54.63; H, 3.60; N, 10.20; residue, 18.8. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3N_2Cu$ requires C, 49.14; H, 3.41; N, 9.55; residue, 26.96%; $C_{24}H_{18}O_4N_4Cu$ requires C, 58.89; H, 3.68; N, 11.45; residue, 16.15%).

Co-ordinatively Unsaturated Copper Complex having Two Copper Atoms from 2-Benzeneazoresorcinol.—To a solution of 2-benzeneazoresorcinol (0.08 g.) in ethanol (20 ml, 70%) containing liquor ammonia (0.8ml) was added dropwise with stirring an ethanolic copper acetate solution (16 ml, 1%). The solution was immediately filtered and diluted with water (20 ml). The precipitate obtained was filtered and washed alternatively with water and dilute ethanol, when a brown powder was obtained; m.p. $> 360^\circ$, yield 0.15g. (Found: C, 39.30; H, 2.46; N, 7.46; residue 41.83. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4N_2Cu_2$ requires C, 38.60; H, 2.68; N, 7.50; residue, 42.62%).

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